

Conductometric Study of the Interaction of Bromamine-B with Silver(I), Mercury(II), Thorium(IV) and Zirconium(IV) Solutions^ψ

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Bromamine-B forms simple salts with silver nitrate and mercuric chloride in aqueous solutions, while thorium chloride, thorium nitrate and zirconium oxychloride react with BAB in aqueous solution to form dibromamine-B. The reactions have been explained by performing conductometric and pH-titrations, thereby substantiating the formation of the free acid, *N*-bromobenzenesulphonamide.

Sodium salt of *N*-bromobenzenesulphonamide or bromamine-B (BAB) has received considerable attention as an oxidimetric reagent^{1,2}. A survey of literature reveals that almost no information on the reaction of BAB with metal ions. As a part of our work on organic haloamines³, we report here the reaction of bromamine-B with Ag^I, Hg^{II}, Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} solutions by performing conductometric titrations supported by pH-titrations, elemental analysis, uv, ir and ¹H nmr studies. The conductometric and pH-titrations of BAB with HCl and H₂SO₄ solutions have also been carried out to supplement the observation.

Results and Discussion

Reaction with silver nitrate : The conductometric titration of different aliquots of solution of silver nitrate (0.05989 *M*) with BAB solution (0.2877 *M*) has been studied. Similarly, in the reverse titrations, different aliquots of BAB solution (0.06324 *M*) was used with silver nitrate solution (0.2942 *M*).

In the direct titration, the conductance of silver nitrate decreases on adding BAB solution. Initially, the pale yellow compound formed dissolves in silver nitrate possibly forming a π -complex⁴ up to the first inflection. The break corresponding to the equivalence point with a molar ratio of 1 : 1 is obtained by extrapolation and the compound formed settles in the solution after the equivalence point. The reaction thus seems to be quantitative and lends support to the formation of a 1 : 1 silver-BAB salt, the silver salt of sulphobromamide (AgBAB). The stoichiometric equation can be represented as

where R = C₆H₅SO₂.

The initial increase in conductance of the BAB solution in the reverse titration is due to the replacement of RNBr⁻ ions with more mobile NO₃⁻ ions. The equivalence point corresponds to a molar ratio of 1 : 1. Thereafter, conductance increases very rapidly due to the excess of AgNO₃ added.

Reaction with mercuric chloride : The conductometric

titration of different aliquots of solution of mercuric chloride (0.04 *M*) with BAB solution (0.2264 *M*) has been studied. In the reverse titrations, different aliquots of BAB solution (0.0217 *M*) was used with mercuric chloride solution (0.1030 *M*). In the first case, the initial increase in conductance of the non-ionic HgCl₂ solution is due to the formation of ionic species. The first point of inflection occurs approximately at a molar ratio of 1 : 1 and the second exactly at 1 : 2 with respect to HgCl₂ and BAB. The stoichiometric equations corresponding to these reactions in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 ratios are represented below forming the mercuric salt of sulphobromamide, Hg(BAB)₂,

In the case of reverse titration, there is a gradual increase in the conductance of BAB solution due to the replacement of the anions RNBr⁻ with the more mobile Cl⁻ ions. Only one point of inflection was obtained and this corresponds to a 1 : 2 molar compound, presumably due to the formation of Hg(BAB)₂. After the equivalence point, a steep decrease in conductance is observed. This can be attributed to the removal of added HgCl₂ by Br⁻ ions present, in the form of complex ions⁵. The stoichiometric equation in the reverse titration is represented as

The results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Conductometric and pH titrations of BAB with HCl, H₂SO₄, Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} solutions : The conductance of different aliquots of solution of HCl (0.01575 *M*) with BAB (0.1446 *M*) decreases in the beginning. After the equivalence point, the conductance increases. A 1 : 1 stoichiometry is noticed, indicating the formation of the free acid, RNHBr. In the reverse titrations ([HCl] = 0.1575 *M* and [BAB] = 0.01446 *M*) there is a slight increase in the conductance, and a rapid increase in conductance is noticed after a 1 : 1 break, again indicating the formation of RNHBr. The pH titrations indicate that the pH increases from 2.40 to 5.00 in the direct titrations and pH decreases from 6.10

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF SILVER NITRATE USING BROMAMINE-B

[BAB] M	[AgNO ₃] (mM)		% Error
	Taken	Found	
0.287 7	1.20	1.21	0.83
0.287 7	1.79	1.78	0.56
0.287 7	2.39	2.41	0.84
0.287 7	2.99	2.97	0.67
0.287 7	3.59	3.62	0.83
0.063 2	5.88	5.92	0.68
0.063 2	8.82	8.87	0.56
0.063 2	11.77	11.82	0.42
0.063 2	14.71	14.65	0.40
0.063 2	17.65	17.72	0.39

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF MERCURIC CHLORIDE USING BROMAMINE-B

[BAB] M	[HgCl ₂] (mM)		% Error
	Taken	Found	
0.226 4	0.80	0.79	1.25
0.226 4	1.20	1.21	0.83
0.226 4	1.60	1.58	1.25
0.226 4	2.00	1.98	1.00
0.226 4	2.40	2.39	0.42
0.021 7	2.06	2.08	0.97
0.021 7	3.09	3.10	0.32
0.021 7	4.13	4.15	0.48
0.021 7	5.15	5.18	0.58
0.021 7	6.18	6.15	0.48

to 2.30 in the reverse titrations of BAB with HCl. The results are shown in Fig. 1. Higuchi *et al.*⁶ studied the disproportionation reaction of chloramine-T. Based on this, it is probable that RNHBr formed around pH 3 disappears above or below this pH giving rise to DBB and RNH₂. Recent studies on the photolysis⁷ of aqueous solutions of BAB revealed the formation of RNBr₂ and RNH₂ as the pH decreases from ~6.0 to ~3.0. A similar conductometric and pH-titrations were observed with ([BAB] = 0.1446 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.01435 M and [H₂SO₄] = 0.1482 M, [BAB] = 0.01446 M) BAB and H₂SO₄ solutions. A 1 : 2 break was noticed with respect to H₂SO₄ : BAB, and the variation of pH was similar to HCl. In the reactions of BAB with HCl or H₂SO₄, there was a formation of golden yellow compound presumed to be dibromamine-B (DBB).

In the direct titration of Zr^{IV} solution ([BAB] = 0.1871 M, [ZrOCl₂] = 0.02129 M), the conductance decreases in the beginning and after the equivalence point, it increases with a 1 : 1 break. In the reverse titrations ([BAB] = 0.01871 M, [ZrOCl₂] = 0.1521 M), the conductance increases slightly and there is a rapid increase after the equivalence point with a 1 : 1 break. The pH titrations were similar to BAB-acid titrations. In the direct titration of Th^{IV} solution ([BAB] = 0.1850 M, [Th(NO₃)₄] = 0.02166 M and [BAB]

= 0.1044 M, [ThCl₄] = 0.01122 M), the conductance plots were similar to Zr^{IV}, except for the break which is observed at 1 : 3 molar ratio corresponding to Th^{IV} : BAB. In the reverse titration of Th^{IV} solution ([BAB] = 0.01896 M [Th(NO₃)₄] = 0.1204 M and [BAB] = 0.01043 M, [ThCl₄] = 0.1122 M), two breaks were noticed, one at 3 : 1 corresponding to BAB : Th^{IV} and the other at 1 : 1 molar ratio. The pH titrations were similar to BAB-acid titrations.

Fig. 1. pH titrations of (a) 40 ml of [HCl] = 0.01575 M with [BAB] = 0.1446 M and (b) 40 ml of [BAB] = 0.01446 M with [HCl] = 0.1575 M.

The golden yellow precipitate formed during the reactions of Zr^{IV} or Th^{IV} with BAB was filtered and the precipitate shaken with dilute H₂SO₄. Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} ions could be detected in the acid solution, while the precipitate was free from these ions. This indicates that Th(OH)₄ and Zr(OH)₄ get adsorbed on the precipitate during the later stages of precipitation. Further, when carefully neutralised solutions of Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} ions with 0.1 M NaOH were mixed with BAB, no precipitation was observed. The conductance increases in these titrations and no break was noticed. These results indicate that hydrogen ions produced during the hydrolysis of these metal ions in aqueous solution is the actual reactant in the precipitation reactions.

The initial decrease in conductance of salt solution when BAB is added could be attributed to the removal of H⁺ ions from the solution, while the increase noted after the break is due to the addition of excess titrant. In the reverse titrations, the initial increase in conductance of the solution is due to the addition of metal ions or chloride ions, although RNBr⁻ ions are removed from the solution by the added H⁺ ions. The steep increase noted after the break is due to the addition of excess titrant (metal ion solution).

Reaction sequence : The hydrolysis equilibria of Th^{IV} ion in aqueous solutions have been studied by several work-

ers⁵. The following equilibria are possible,

indicating that the hexamer $\text{Th}_6(\text{OH})_{15}^{9+}$ is the important species present in Th^{IV} ion solutions. The hydrolysis⁹ of ZrOCl_2 is

It is seen that three H^+ ions and one H^+ ion per mole are available from the hydrolysis equilibria of Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} ion solutions respectively. By a knowledge of these hydrolysis equilibria, an explanation of the breaks observed in the conductance plots can be given. The turbidity obtained in the conductometric titrations could be dibromamine-B (DBB) (RNBr_2) which is only sparingly soluble in water (0.1662 g dm^{-3} at 25°). The break obtained at 1 : 1 molar ratio with respect to BAB and Zr^{IV} ion probably indicates the formation of RNHBr . The break observed at 3 : 1 with respect to BAB and Th^{IV} ion solutions and for BAB and H_2SO_4 at 2 : 1 mole ratio could possibly indicate the number of protons available for the formation of the free acid.

With the above results in view and the work of Hardy and Johnston¹, the following equilibria are possible with BAB in acid solutions,

Product analysis : The golden precipitate obtained in the above experiments was suspected to be dibromamine-B (DBB). DBB was characterised by the estimation of active halogen content iodometrically in glacial acetic acid medium¹⁰, m.p. (110°) and other details : AgBAB : λ_{max} (H_2O) 216.4 (p), 269 nm (s), ν_{max} 2 950 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C-H}}$), 1 580 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C=C}}$), 1 150 (SO_2 sym), 1 330 cm^{-1} (SO_2 asym), δ (CDCl_3) 7.4–8.1 (5H, m, ArH); $\text{Hg}(\text{BAB})_2$: λ_{max} (H_2O) 216.4 (p), 262 nm (s), ν_{max} 2 960 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C-H}}$), 1 580 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C=C}}$), 1 140 (SO_2 sym), 1 300 cm^{-1} (SO_2 asym), δ (CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6) 7.4–8.1 (10H, m, ArH); DBB : λ_{max} (H_2O) 219.2 (p), 267 nm (s), ν_{max} 2 950 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C-H}}$), 1 580 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C=C}}$), 1 170 (SO_2 sym), 1 310 cm^{-1} (SO_2 asym). All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis. The uv spectra of AgBAB , $\text{Hg}(\text{BAB})_2$ and DBB are characteristic of ben-

zenoid absorption and can probably be attributed to π - π transition. It may be noted that benzenesulphonamide absorbs in this region.¹¹ An attempt was made to check for mass balance in all the reactions similar to chloramine-T¹². The results were unsuccessful due to the solubility of DBB in the metal ion solution in the initial stages.

Properties of AgBAB and $\text{Hg}(\text{BAB})_2$: The compounds are pale yellow crystalline solids. On heating, AgBAB decomposes at 150–154° and $\text{Hg}(\text{BAB})_2$ at 148–152°. Further, AgBAB is sensitive to light and gradually turns violet upon exposure to sunlight. AgBAB is slightly soluble in water (0.362 g dm^{-3} at 30°), chloroform and alcohol, but it is fairly soluble in large excess of silver nitrate solution. $\text{Hg}(\text{BAB})_2$ is slightly soluble in water (0.269 g dm^{-3} at 30°), alcohol, CHCl_3 and CCl_4 . The compounds behave as electrolytes in aqueous solution. Aqueous solutions of AgBAB and $\text{Hg}(\text{BAB})_2$ liberate iodine from acidified potassium iodide solution. Stoichiometric amounts of iodine are liberated with AgBAB almost instantaneously, but the yields are not stoichiometric in the case of $\text{Hg}(\text{BAB})_2$.

Conclusion : The reactions are simple, rapid and could be used to estimate Ag^{I} and Hg^{II} in aqueous solutions. DBB could be prepared by the reaction of BAB with Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} in aqueous solutions. An experimental proof for the formation of RNHBr ($\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2$) is demonstrated. The silver salt of BAB formed may be used as an oxidising agent.

Experimental

A Systronics 304 conductivity meter and a Elico LI-120 pH-meter were used. A dip type conductivity cell with a cell constant 1.0 cm^{-1} , was used. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Jasco UVIDEC 610 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Jeol FX 90 Q (90 MHz) spectrometer.

BAB was prepared¹³ from benzenesulphonamide (Aldrich). Silver nitrate, mercuric chloride, thorium nitrate, thorium chloride (all B.D.H.) and zirconium oxychloride (Riedel) were used. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Triple-distilled water was used (sp. cond. < 1.0 $\times 10^{-6}$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) to prepare all solutions. An aqueous solution of BAB (0.01–0.3 M) was standardised by iodometric method. Solutions of metal ions (0.01–0.3 M), HCl (0.015–0.15 M) and H_2SO_4 (0.014–0.15 M) were prepared.

Procedure : The initial conductance of a known volume of either metal ion solution or the acid solution of known concentration was measured. The this solution, BAB solution (5–10 times stronger) was added in small volumes. The conductance of the solution was measured only after stirring and the product formed was allowed to settle. Conductance of the solution after each addition of BAB solu-

tion, was calculated after applying the volume correction¹⁴. The equivalence point was obtained graphically by plotting the corrected conductance of the solution against the volume of BAB added. Reverse titrations were carried out in the same manner. Similarly, pH titrations were carried out for all the solutions, except silver nitrate and mercuric chloride.

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References

1. F. E. HARDY and J. P. JOHNSTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1973, 742.
2. B. N. USHA, H. S. YATHIRAJAN and RANGASWAMY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 685; S. KOTHARI and K. K. BANERJI, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1985, **63**, 2726; T. A. IYENGAR, D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and PUTTASWAMY, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1992, **104**, 611.
3. H. S. YATHIRAJAN, D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and RANGASWAMY, *Talanta*, 1980, **27**, 52; RANGASWAMY, B. N. USHA and H. S. YATHIRAJAN, *Analyst*, 1984, **109**, 101; B. N. USHA, RANGASWAMY and H. S. YATHIRAJAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 812.
4. E. S. GOULD, "Mechanism and Structure of Organic Chemistry", Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York, 1959.
5. E. S. GOULD, "Inorganic Reactions and Structure", Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York, 1962.
6. T. HIGUCHI, K. IKEDA and A. HUSSAIN, *J. Chem. Soc.(B)*, 1967, 546.
7. K. N. MOHANA, H. S. YATHIRAJAN, A. S. ANANDA MURTHY and K. M. L. RAI, *Astan J. Chem.*, 1997, 9.
8. K. PAN and T. M. HSEU, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1955, **28**, 162; R. PRASAD and A. K. DAY, *Kolloid Z.*, 1961, **175**, 136; R. P. SINGH and N. R. BANERJI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 255; C. F. BAES, N. J. MEYER and C. E. ROBERTS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 518; K. A. KRAUS and R. W. HOLMBERG, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 325.
9. K. SHEAN-SHYA and TUYEN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1959, **53**, 7827.
10. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and M. S. AHMED, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 590.
11. J. R. DYER, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice-Hall, New Jersey, 1965.
12. R. SWAMY and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 463.
13. M. S. AHMED and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Talanta*, 1980, **27**, 669.
14. L. MEITES and H. C. THOMAS, "Advanced Analytical Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1958.